

STUDIES ON THE ADSORPTION FROM NON-AQUEOUS SOLVENTS. PART I

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The adsorption of benzoic, *o*-nitrobenzoic and phthalic acids at different concentrations from various non-aqueous solvents has been studied and the relation between the adsorption of solutes and the molecular properties of the solvents such as polarity, solubility and dipole moment has been discussed.

From the survey of literature it is revealed that much work has not been done on the adsorption of solutes from non-aqueous solvents. The important contributions on the subject are those of Freundlich (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1906, 57, 385), Firth (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, 16, 434), Ostwald and Izaguirre (*Kolloid Z.*, 1922, 30, 279), Patrik and Jones (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1), Alekseevskii (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 59, 1033), Heyne and Polyanyi (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 132, 384), Nekrassov (*ibid.*, 1928, 136, 18), Mc.Kelvey (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 1522), Trividic (*Compt. rend.*, 1928, 186, 865), Heymann and Boye (*Naturwiss.*, 1930, 18, 157; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, 160, 219), Berger (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1931, 50, 377), Ockrend (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 613), Ermolenko and Ginzburg (*Colloid J., U. S. S. R.*, 1939, 5, 263), Ermolenko and Bokhvala (*Acta Phys. Chem., U. S. S. R.*, 1940, 13, 839), Papps and Othmer (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1944, 36, 430), and others. These authors have mainly studied the adsorption of various organic acids and iodine from non-aqueous solvents using different adsorbents and have not used any non-polar substance. Hence, they could not give a definite relationship between the nature of the solvents and the polarity of the solutes as regards adsorption. In the present work an attempt has been made to correlate the nature of the solute and the solvent with the amount of the solute adsorbed by the adsorbent and hence different combinations of polar and non-polar acids have been taken. In this paper solutes are polar acids; the solvents taken are both polar and non-polar. The amounts of these acids adsorbed by animal charcoal have been determined.

EXPERIMENTAL

All chemicals used were from B. D. H. The solvents were purified by standard methods and solutes were recrystallised and dried. Animal charcoal used was chemically pure and was free from phosphate and chloride. It was sieved through mesh 360 μ /sq. cm. It was used after drying at 110°.

Solutions of known concentrations were prepared and 10 c.c. of these solutions were taken in test tubes with constriction at the neck containing 0.5 g. of animal charcoal. The necks were then immediately sealed. These sealed test tubes were put in a shaker fitted in an air thermostat and shaken for twenty four hours at a constant temperature and then the tubes were broken at the neck and the contents were centrifuged to allow the charcoal to settle. Known quantities of the supernatant solution were then

quickly analysed by titrating with standard carbonate-free barium hydroxide solution using phenolphthalein as the indicator. By subtracting the values of equilibrium concentration from the values of the original concentration, adsorption was calculated and recorded in millimoles/litre. The values of the amount adsorbed at 0.5 concentration along with the values of dipole moment (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, 30, appendix), dielectric constant (Landolt Börnstein "Tabellen") and solubilities (Seidell, "Solubility of Organic Compounds", Vol. II, 1941) obtained from the tables are given in Table I and in the other tables adsorption only is given. The physical properties at other concentrations have not been given as the solvents used are the same as in Table I.

TABLE I

Solvent.	Dielectric constant (e. s. u.)	Dipole moment (Debye units).	Benzoic acid		o-Nitrobenzoic acid		Phthalic acid	
			* Solu- bility.	Adsorp- tion.	* Solu- bility.	Adsorp- tion.	* Solu- bility.	Adsorp- tion.
CCl ₄	2.21	0	0.0593	103.0	—	—	—	—
Benzene	2.27	0	0.0819	65.9	—	—	—	—
Toluene	2.34	0.37	0.0855	53.7	—	—	—	—
o-Xylenc	2.58 at 17°	0.60	—	83.5	—	—	—	—
m-Xylenc	2.35	0.40	0.0889	45.0	—	—	—	—
MeOH	32.0	1.68	0.1689	51.3	56.6	69.4	5.125	68.4
EtOH	25.0	1.70	0.1882	51.0	30.4	88.1	4.265	70.9
n-PrOH	22.0	1.70	0.1810	49.8	21.5	98.9	2.732	140.7
n-BuOH	19.2	1.70	0.1968	49.6	10.7	112.2	2.231	144.6
Acetone	21.0	2.9	0.2141	42.3	—	73.0	2.896	95.5
Chlorobenzene	11.0	1.56	0.1047	38.2	—	—	—	—
Nitrobenzene	36.0	4.23	0.1081	29.9	—	—	—	—

* Solubility of benzoic acid and phthalic acid is in g. moles of acid per 1.0 g. mol. sat. solution and of o-nitrobenzoic acid in g. per 100 g. of solvent.

TABLE II

Temp. = 30°.

Solvent.	Adsorption of benzoic acid in m. moles/litre at concentration					
	0.6.	0.55.	0.4.	0.3.	0.2.	0.1.
CCCl ₄	115.0	109.5	87.5	73.5	56.0	36.5
Benzene	72.5	—	59.5	52.5	43.5	32.0
Toluene	57.5	—	47.2	40.2	32.0	21.6
o-Xylene	93.5	—	72.5	62.5	49.0	33.0
m-Xylene	48.5	—	41.1	36.0	29.6	21.5
MeOH	56.5	53.3	46.0	39.1	31.2	21.5
EtOH	56.2	53.6	45.1	39.0	31.0	21.4
n-PrOH	55.9	53.1	46.0	38.7	30.8	—
n-BuOH	55.7	53.0	45.8	38.6	30.7	20.9
Acetone	46.0	44.6	38.7	34.0	28.2	21.1
Chlorobenzene	41.4	40.0	34.9	31.0	26.5	20.0
Nitrobenzene	33.1	31.3	26.2	22.3	19.1	—

TABLE III

Temp. = 30°.

Solvent.	Adsorption of <i>o</i> -nitrobenzoic acid in m. moles/litre at conc.				
	0.4.	0.3.	0.2.	0.1.	0.05.
Methyl alcohol	60.3	50.0	39.4	26.8	20.4
Ethyl alcohol	75.3	61.7	46.4	30.3	21.6
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	85.9	70.7	53.5	31.2	22.2
Acetone	61.1	48.3	34.7	27.0	21.1
<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	96.8	78.5	58.3	34.4	24.5

TABLE IV

Temp. = 30°.

Solvent.	Adsorption of phthalic acid in m. moles/litre at conc.				
	0.4.	0.3.	0.2.	0.1.	0.05.
Methyl alcohol	59.2	49.0	37.9	25.2	19.6
Ethyl alcohol	59.0	48.0	34.5	26.6	20.8
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	118.5	93.7	64.9	34.9	23.7
<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	121.5	95.9	65.8	36.1	24.9
Acetone	85.4	69.1	46.5	32.3	22.8

DISCUSSION

The solvents taken here have been divided into three groups: (1) group of substances having no dipole moment; (2) group of alcohols of the same homologous series and (3) group including acetone and substituted benzenes (highly polar)

The adsorption will be considered here from the view point of polarity, solubility and dipole moment.

Most direct evidence of polarity is the dielectric constant. The magnitude of this constant indicates the moment of the polar groups within the liquids or the displacement of the electrons or both. So, for polarity dielectric constant will be considered. It is found from the data that adsorption of benzoic acid in Gr. (1) decreases with increasing dielectric constant, *i.e.* polarity of the solvent; in Gr. (2) it is nearly constant, and in Gr. (3), leaving chlorobenzene, it decreases with increasing dielectric constant, *i.e.* polarity.

The adsorption of *o*-nitrobenzoic acid and phthalic acid decreases with increasing polarity of the solvent (acetone alone is an exception).

From the solubility data it is seen that as solubility of the solute in the solvent increases, adsorption becomes less and less which means that a reciprocal relation exists between solubility and adsorption. The rule is obeyed by groups (1) and (2) and (excepting acetone) by Gr. (3) also. Similar relation between the adsorption and solubility have been obtained by Firth (*loc. cit.*) and Patric and Jones (*loc. cit.*).

From the considerations of the dipole moment it is found that in Gr. (1) with increasing dipole moment adsorption decreases (excepting *o*-xylene). In Gr. (2) dipole moment is constant as also the adsorption value of benzoic acid remains constant. But adsorption of *o*-nitrobenzoic acid and phthalic acid increases as we ascend the homologous series of alcohols. In Gr. (3) chlorobenzene is an exception, otherwise with increasing dipole moment adsorption decreases. So weak adsorption occurs in strongly polar solvents and strong adsorption in weakly polar solvents. This antitatic relation between dipole moment and adsorption is not universal, however, and is probably influenced by the mutual affinities of the solutes and the solvents, as pointed out by Heymann and Boye (*loc. cit.*).

Now as molecules of the solutes taken here are partly polar and partly non-polar, it will be expected that their solubility will be less in highly polar and non-polar solvents, while adsorption will be high, and as solubility will be greater in the intermediate solvents, adsorption will be low. It has been observed that this is true because adsorption of benzoic acid is high in non-polar solvents and is less in intermediate solvents. But adsorption is also low in highly polar solvents of Gr. (3) which is due to the mutual effect, as pointed out above.

The polarity of the three solutes taken is in the following order: phthalic acid > *o*-nitrobenzoic acid > benzoic acid.

So solubility in any solvent, say *n*-butyl alcohol, should be least of phthalic acid and most of benzoic acid. And so the adsorption in a solvent should be most of phthalic acid and least of benzoic acid. This is also true to a great extent.

Similarly it can be predicated that as the solubility of non-polar solutes will be much in non-polar solvents, adsorption will be low and in polar solvents solubility will be low and adsorption will be high.

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